

IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF MEDICAL CARE FOR ELDERLY AND SENILE PATIENTS WITH SUBJECTIVELY UNMANIFESTED ISCHEMIC HEART DISEASE.

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Abstract: The problem of subjectively unmanifested coronary heart disease is becoming increasingly urgent in view of improved diagnostics, early detection of coronary heart disease, and wider introduction of invasive diagnostic methods. In this regard, especially in patients of older age groups, a special approach to the issues of diagnostics and treatment of this pathology is necessary to improve the quality of medical care provided to them.

The purpose of the study: to develop an optimal algorithm for examination and treatment of patients of older age groups with subjectively unmanifested form of coronary heart disease in a multidisciplinary hospital to improve the quality of medical care for this group of patients.

Objective: to create an algorithm for medical examination and treatment of patients of older age groups with subjectively unmanifested form of ischemic heart disease.

Materials and methods: recruitment of patients with subjectively unmanifested form of ischemic heart disease (IHD) into two main groups — elderly and senile — and two control groups of patients with clinically manifested IHD — elderly and senile. It is planned to recruit about 100 people for each group. Each group is divided into two subgroups by gender. Patients of all groups undergo the following: assessment of complaints and anamnesis according to the scheme; assessment of pre-test probability of ischemic heart disease;

risk assessment according to the SCORE scale; physical examination; general clinical blood and urine tests, as well as a study of biochemical laboratory parameters; ECG; ECHOCG; assessment of tolerance to physical activity using a test with a six-minute walk; SMEKG; stress echocardiography or bicycle ergometry; coronary angiography; lipid spectrum assessment; thyroid status assessment; glycemic profile assessment; plasma brain natriuretic peptide activity study; high-sensitivity troponin I concentration assessment in blood serum; assessment of the presence and severity of anxiety and depression in the patient; quality of life assessment; pain and vibration sensitivity assessment.

Results: currently, 25 people have been recruited into the groups: 15 in the main groups (8 and 7, respectively) and 10 (5 and 5) in the control groups. **CLINICAL GERONTOLOGY. Conclusion:** analysis of literary data shows the need for a comprehensive approach to the problem of subjectively unmanifested coronary heart disease in older patients. It is necessary to take into account the gender characteristics of subjectively unmanifested coronary heart disease in elderly and senile patients. There is a need for dynamic psychotherapeutic support of elderly and senile patients with subjectively unmanifested form of coronary heart disease. A personalized approach to treatment should be used in **ACADEMIC INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON MULTI-DISCIPLINARY STUDIES AND EDUCATION** Hosted from Pittsburgh, USA 87 multidisciplinary hospital settings for elderly and senile patients with subjectively unmanifested form of coronary heart disease.

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